

SUB-CENTENNIAL OSCILLATIONS IN THE GEOMAGNETIC FIELD AND EARTH'S ROTATION

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A field in which progress has recently been made regards deciphering the relationship between the evolution of the geomagnetic field and the Earth's rotation. Fluctuation in the Earth's rotation rate (or spin rate) is expressed by the so-called excess length of day (ΔLOD), *i.e.* variations from the sidereal day. The rotation of the solid Earth changes as a result of applied external torques, internal mass redistribution (in which we include the time dependent fluid convection in the outer core), and the hydrodynamic or magneto-hydrodynamic stresses acting at the fluid/solid Earth interfaces. Generally, the Earth's rotation is governed by the conservation of the angular momentum of the Earth, with transfers between the solid part (inner core plus mantle) and fluid volumes in contact with (atmosphere and oceans, on one hand, and outer core, on the other). A detailed account on LOD variations can be found in the review papers of Gross (2007) and Dehant and Mathews (2007).

Both Earth's rotation speed and the geomagnetic field are characterized by temporal variations at several time scales, from seconds to centuries. At long timescales, the observation of Le Mouél *et al.* (1981) of a relationship between the magnetic declination time derivative and the Earth's rotation rate, interpreted by the authors as being caused by geomagnetic jerks, is well known. The so-called torsional oscillations in the outer core, that have been forwarded by Zatman and Bloxham (1997) to explain geomagnetic jerks, result in LOD variations (oscillations) of similar periods (Roberts *et al.*, 2007). The latter authors estimate, by deploying the Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) method of Huang *et al.* (1988), that in both LOD and geomagnetic field (declination, D, and inclination, I) well correlated similar periodicities with a period of about 60 years are present, indicating as a mechanism the torsional oscillations (see the discussion and references on the subject therein).

We have previously identified oscillations in the secular variation of the geomagnetic field, at sub-centennial (60-90 years) and inter-decadal (20-30 years) timescales (*e.g.*, Demetrescu and Dobrica, 2014; Dobrica *et al.*, 2018). Also, we find such variations to be present in the long-term evolution of the geomagnetic activity (geomagnetic index *aa*). In the present paper, we link such variations to fluctuations in Earth's rotation rate (length of day, LOD), which we find to develop at the same timescales. We also describe a plausible causal chain, from oscillations of the magnetospheric ring current intensity at similar timescales, via Alfvén waves in the outer core, to corresponding coaxial geostrophic cylinders that carry the necessary angular momentum changes to produce length of day fluctuations. To identify oscillations at the two time scales in all three processes invoked, we use the Hodrick and Prescott (1997) filtering method to separate the analysed time series into a trend plus a cyclic component at short timescale (decennial) and, subsequently, Butterworth filtering to single out the sub-centennial and inter-decadal constituents of the trend that characterize the three processes considered. A cross-correlation analysis of the corresponding time series is performed. We compare data and singled out constituents regarding (1) dD/dt at Niemegek geomagnetic

observatory – standing for oscillations in the geomagnetic field, (2) IERS LOD time series – standing for the Earth’s rotation rate, (3) a reconstructed back to 1868 geomagnetic index Dst (available only since 1957) – standing for the intensity of the magnetospheric ring current.

The main results of the above research are illustrated in the next two figures.

Fig. 1. (a) Comparison of trends in LOD (red), geomagnetic field (dD/dt at NGK, (black), and magnetospheric ring current intensity (reconstructed Dst, green); (b) the same for the sub-centennial constituents

External variable source at sub-centennial (60-90 years) and inter-decadal (20-30 years) timescales

- magnetospheric ring
- auroral + equatorial electrojets

Fig. 2. The schematic causal chain worked out for the sub-centennial variations observed in LOD and in the geomagnetic field

Concluding remarks

- The LOD time series shows oscillations at sub-centennial (60-90 years) and inter-decadal (20-35 years) timescales, with amplitudes of 1.5 ms and, respectively, 1 ms, correlatable ($r \sim 0.8$) with known variations in the geomagnetic field (dD/dt) at the same timescales;
- A similar temporal structure is seen in the magnetospheric ring current evolution. Variations in this current might be the ultimate driver of variations observed in both geomagnetic field and LOD;
- The causal chain: long-term variations in the external, ring current field penetrate the conductive outer core (~ 30 km) and induce Alfvén waves when interacting with the core magnetic field: torsional oscillations observed at surface as variable field constituents at the two timescales;
- Future work: extension to the intra-decadal variation (“6-years”) in LOD (amplitude ~ 0.15 ms)

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